

Fig. B.1: Redshift histograms of two lens candidates as example, one visually identified to be in an overdense environment (HSC J0214-0206, red) and one not (HSC J0014+0041, blue). We show the original histograms (top panel), the histograms where the median distribution of 10 000 random sightlines are subtracted from the original (middle panel), and the normalized histograms (bottom panel) where the subtracted histograms are normalized by the standard deviation of the 10 000 sightlines. Our defined criteria, introduced in Sect. 4.3 are indicated with brown (OD_{vis}) and gray (not OD_{vis}) lines. In detail, the vertical solid line indicates z_{low} , the lower bound of the tallest redshift bin of the histogram. The height of this bin, denoted as N_{max} , is marked by the dashed horizontal line. The lengths of the horizontal solid lines, which are the number of the shaded bins, represent N_{peak5} and N_{peak10} , while the sum of objects in all the shaded bins corresponds to the value of A_{peak5} and A_{peak10} . See Appendix B for further details.

Table B.2: Comparison of true-positive (TP) and false-positive (FP) rates for different selection criteria using the photometric redshift distributions around the 546 grade A or B lens candidates after subtracting a median distribution from 10 000 random sky positions.

No.	Criteria									visual insp.		Literature		F1 statistics		
	$N_{\max}$	z_{low}	z_{low}	N_{tot}	N_{frac}	N_{peak5}	A_{peak5}	N_{peak10}	A_{peak10}	TP	FP	TP	FP	$F1_{\text{vis}}$	$F1_{\text{lit}}$	$F1_{\text{tot}}$
1	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	69	240	134	175	0.370	0.555	0.474
2	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	66	194	118	142	0.407	0.544	0.485
3	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	53	147	98	101	0.402	0.525	0.474
4	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	60	222	116	155	0.347	0.521	0.445
5	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	57	176	100	122	0.384	0.505	0.453
6	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	44	129	80	81	0.371	0.478	0.434
7	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	69	196	121	144	0.419	0.551	0.495
8	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	66	159	106	119	0.457	0.531	0.500
9	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	53	126	91	87	0.436	0.517	0.484
10	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	60	181	105	126	0.393	0.519	0.465
11	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	57	144	90	101	0.430	0.493	0.467
12	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	44	111	75	69	0.402	0.472	0.443
13	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	67	187	123	131	0.421	0.575	0.509
14	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	64	148	107	105	0.464	0.554	0.517
15	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 0	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	51	108	88	71	0.457	0.529	0.500
16	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	60	177	110	122	0.399	0.542	0.481
17	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	57	138	94	96	0.440	0.516	0.485
18	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 1.0	≥ 50	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	44	98	75	62	0.427	0.482	0.460
19	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	67	151	111	107	0.475	0.566	0.528
20	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	64	118	96	86	0.520	0.539	0.532
21	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	51	91	82	60	0.495	0.519	0.510
22	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	60	143	99	100	0.449	0.531	0.497
23	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	57	110	84	79	0.494	0.499	0.496
24	≥ 16	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.13	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	44	83	70	53	0.461	0.471	0.467
25	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 3	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 0	66	151	107	128	0.470	0.523	0.501
26	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 3	≥ 30	≥ 0	≥ 0	65	146	106	114	0.473	0.538	0.511
27	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 24	61	121	102	90	0.496	0.557	0.533
28	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 30	60	114	100	82	0.504	0.562	0.539
29	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 3	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 0	63	118	93	88	0.514	0.524	0.520
30	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 3	≥ 30	≥ 0	≥ 0	62	113	92	83	0.519	0.527	0.524
31	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 24	58	88	89	67	0.552	0.539	0.544
32	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 30	57	83	87	61	0.559	0.540	0.548
33	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 3	≥ 35	≥ 0	≥ 0	65	133	104	97	0.496	0.555	0.531
34	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.07	≥ 3	≥ 40	≥ 0	≥ 0	64	123	102	87	0.510	0.562	0.541
35	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 2	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 24	58	128	97	89	0.464	0.539	0.508
36	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.07	≥ 2	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 30	58	115	93	80	0.489	0.536	0.517
37	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 3	≥ 35	≥ 0	≥ 0	62	100	90	75	0.549	0.531	0.538
38	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 0	≥ 0.10	≥ 3	≥ 40	≥ 0	≥ 0	61	91	88	66	0.565	0.537	0.548
39	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 2	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 24	55	94	84	65	0.516	0.520	0.519
40	≥ 11	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 2	≥ 20	≥ 0	≥ 30	55	84	80	59	0.542	0.511	0.523
41	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 24	57	83	87	62	0.559	0.539	0.546
42	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 0	≥ 2	≥ 30	57	80	86	59	0.567	0.539	0.550
43	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 35	≥ 2	≥ 24	57	80	86	58	0.567	0.541	0.551
44	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 45	≥ 2	≥ 24	56	74	82	52	0.577	0.532	0.550
45	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 35	≥ 2	≥ 30	57	78	85	57	0.573	0.538	0.551
46	≥ 15	≥ 0.1	≤ 0.8	≥ 50	≥ 0.10	≥ 0	≥ 45	≥ 2	≥ 30	56	73	81	52	0.580	0.528	0.548

Notes. We distinguish between lens candidates classified as clusters during visual inspection (see Sect. 4.2) and based on galaxy catalogs (Oguri 2014; Oguri et al. 2018; Wen & Han 2018, 2021). Without photo-z selection (see No. 0 in Table B.1), we visually identified 84 lens candidates to be in an overdense environment, while 174 lens candidates are located closer than 100'' from a known galaxy cluster.

Fig. B.2: Normalized histograms of our eight introduced selection criteria using the subtracted photo- z distributions. We distinguish between lens candidates visually identified to be in an overdensity (blue) or through the galaxy cluster catalogs (green), compared to those not in an overdensity (orange and magenta, respectively).

Fig. B.3: Normalized histograms of our eight introduced selection criteria using the normalized photo- z distributions (which are the subtracted histograms in Fig. B.1) normalized by the standard deviation of the 10 000 random sightlines' histograms). We distinguish between lens candidates visually identified to be in an overdensity (blue) or through the galaxy cluster catalogs (green), compared to those not in an overdensity (orange and magenta, respectively).

Fig. B.4: New grade A and B group- or cluster lens candidates based on visual inspection. Continuation of Fig. 4

Fig. [B.4](#) continued: New grade A and B group- or cluster lens candidates based on visual inspection.

Fig. B.4 continued: New grade A and B group- or cluster lens candidates based on visual inspection.

Fig. [B.4](#) continued: New grade A and B group- or cluster lens candidates based on visual inspection.